

		Use cases		
Hybridization Characteristics (HC)	Description	JNEM-Parameter-identification	JNEM-Parameter-estimation	JNEM-Parameter-validation
Overview/Context	Describe the digital twin system in which hybridization is considered.	There is a 1D simulation model used to cover services such as debit simulation, cavity detection, etc...	There is a 1D simulation model used to cover services such as debit simulation, cavity detection, etc...	There is a 1D simulation model used to cover services such as debit simulation, cavity detection, etc...
Problem Statement	Describes the difficulty to be overcome, the obstacle to be surmounted in terms of value streams and causality, not as a combination of models	The simulation model is calibrated once at creation, with fixed parameters during operation. As the physical system evolves (e.g., degradation, changing conditions), discrepancies emerge between simulated and measured behaviors, leading to reduced service reliability and decreasing fidelity.	The simulation model is calibrated once at creation, with fixed parameters during operation. As the physical system evolves (e.g., degradation, changing conditions), discrepancies emerge between simulated and measured behaviors, leading to reduced service reliability and decreasing fidelity. How to obtain a model that infer updated value (or a correction law) based on the parameter to be adjusted, in order to restore the consistency of the twin.	The simulation model is calibrated once at creation, with fixed parameters during operation. As the physical system evolves (e.g., degradation, changing conditions), discrepancies emerge between simulated and measured behaviors, leading to reduced service reliability and decreasing fidelity. How to ensure the 1D model used is following the behaviors of the original system.
Existing Twin Assets(models, data, ...) & Gaps	Characterizes the digital-twin environment in which hybridization is introduced, providing the initial operational and modeling context from which the hybrid solution emerges.	The digital twin is built around a one-dimensional simulation model supporting services such as flow-rate prediction and cavity detection.	The digital twin is built around a one-dimensional simulation model supporting services such as flow-rate prediction and cavity detection. There is an inductive model which identify which parameters must be estimate in order to have a dynamic prameters for the 1D model	The digital twin is built around a one-dimensional simulation model supporting services such as flow-rate prediction and cavity detection. There is an inductive model that estimates a new value for a parameter based on the current operating conditions of the 1D model.
Intended Deliverable Capability (IDC)	Defines the operational challenge that motivates hybridization, expressed in terms of system behavior, value generation, and causal relationships rather than model integration.	Determine which calibration parameters of the 1D model must be adjusted to explain the discrepancy observed between the physical system and its digital twin counterpart.	Infer updated parameter values, or correction law, capable of restoring consistency between the digital twin and the physical system.	Ensure that the updated 1D model remains representative of the evolving behavior of the physical system throughout operation.

Conceptual Requirements	Describe the non-functional requirements that the hybridisation implementation must meet in order to be acceptable in the given context.	The model must identify the parameter responsible for a discrepancy within the limits of observability defined by the available measurements and operating conditions; identification shall ensure that parameter contributions are distinguishable, enabling attribution of discrepancies to a reduced set of candidate parameters.	The model must estimate the value of the target parameter under the defined operating envelope, based on control inputs (running conditions like temperature), measures from the physical system and current nominal parameters	Any parameter update must be validated against a dedicated dataset or validation window; the process shall always produce a usable parameter set, either by accepting the updated parameter or retaining the previous valid parameter
Deliverable Quality	Defines the expected functional capability delivered by hybridization, expressed as a transformation or decision-making capability independent of implementation architecture.	Outputs must ensure low latency and stable estimates, remaining compatible with DT real-time services without disrupting simulations	Outputs must ensure low latency and stable estimates, remaining compatible with DT real-time services without disrupting simulations	Parameter updates must include a fidelity assessment; if alignment with the physical system cannot be ensured (e.g., failed recalibration), the resulting degradation in fidelity must be detected and propagated to the dependent services.